

Response Letter to Data Mangement Plan of Retrieving SSH Journals Citation Information from three datasets (COCI, META and ERIH-PLUS) Review.

First of all, we would like to thank Seyedali Ghasempouri for his review of our Data Management Plan¹. We have tried to take into account all the issues raised by the author, and we have also changed one of the subjects of this work which, even if not explicitly pointed out, was erroneous.

In fact, we have finally produced a version of this DMP centered on both the software we want to develop, but also on a newly devised dataset. We will try to follow the ordering of the original review for better clarity. Thus, starting from the section about the overall clarity and organization, we have tried to add some layers of clarity to our work, in particular to explain in a better manner some obscure points. Despite that, we did not add a table of contents to our work, mainly because we did not find the possibility of this addition in the template we have followed on Argos.

Nonetheless, we think that the work is pretty easy to follow, being it divided in two main sections, each of which taking into account one of the two outcomes of our project. Going straight to the following section, we have declared that we will use vocabularies for both the dataset and software's metadata, as suggested by the author of the review. Additionally, we have also specified which vocabularies we will use in our project.

Furthermore, for what concerns quality assurance procedures, we have decided to avoid them, mainly because - for what concerns the dataset - we have stated out many times that the data we collect are secondary data, derived from reliable sources, all of them are linked inside the DMP. Subsequently, we dealt with the storage related section, which has been enriched with details about the different ways in which we plan to secure our data. For what concerns instead potential difficulties in data sharing, we left the situation unchanged, mainly because we cannot see such problems if we decide, as stated, to make everything open and freely available. In this point could have been nice to understand whether the author of the review see such difficulties. If that is the case, could be pretty helpful for us if these could be pointed out in an explicit manner. Differently from the previous point, we benefit from the observations about data reuse. We devised some strategies to meaningfully deal with our support.

In conclusion, we would like to thank again the reviewer for his work, and encourage him to answer to our new version in order to devise "together" the best possible solution for the issues in our work.

¹ Seyedali Ghasempouri. (2023). Review of: "Data Mangement Plan of Retrieving SSH Journals Citation Information from three datasets (COCI, META and ERIH-PLUS)". Qeios. doi:10.32388/7CLRJX.